

MAKTAB GEOMETRIYA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA DASTURLASH TILLARIDAN FOYDALANISH

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Ma'lumki, jamiyat rivojlangani sari iqtisodiyot, fan, texnika, texnologiya, madaniyat, san'at, tibbiyot kabilarning turli masalalari haqidagi mavjud ma'lumotlar, axborot zahiralaridan foydalanishni tashkil etish, intellektual va iqtisodiy hayotga tobora ko'proq ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Fan - texnikaning rivojlanishi natijasida hozirgi kunga kelib, har bir sohada ijobiy natijalarga erishilmoqda. Mamlakatimizning istiqbolli kelajagini, uning taraqqiyotini, rivojlanish bosqichlarini yangi texnologiyalardan foydalanmasdan tasavvur etish mumkin emas.

Zamonaviy kompyuterlarda turli zamonaviy dasturlash tillari keng ko'lamda qo'llanilmoqda. Bu dasturlar iqtisodiyot, boshqarish, xizmat ko'rsatish va ayniqsa, sanoat va ishlab chiqarishning turli sohalarida muhim ahamiyatga molik masalalarni hal qilishda ba'zan yagona omilga aylanmoqda. Bu esa o'z navbatida muhandislik va boshqarish sohasi xodimlari uchun kompyuterlardan unumli va oqilona foydalanishni taqozo etadi.

Shu jumladan, ta'lim sohasida ham zamonaviy dasturlash tillari va mana shu dasturlash tillari orqali yaratilgan dasturiy vositalar keng qo'llanilmoqda. Bugungi kunda ta'lim sifatini yanada oshirish va vaqtdan unumli foydalangan holda sifatli, kerakli va ko'p bilimga ega bo'lish eng dolzarb masaladir. Zamonaviy dasturlash tili hisoblangan Delphi dasturlash tilida yaratilgan, matematikani o'rganuvchilar uchun qulay bo'lgan amaliy dastur ushbu dolzarb masalaga munosib yechim bo'la oladi. Delphi dasturlash tilida yaratilgan amaliy dasturning mazmun mohiyati shundan iboratki, bu amaliy dasturda xoh algebraik, xoh geometrik masala bo'lsin uning yechimini topish, geometrik shakllarning chizmalarini tasvirini ko'rish mumkin.

Quyida keltiriladigan misolda uchburchakning yuzini hisoblash uchun amaliy dastur tuzilgan. Ushbu dasturda uchburchakning yuzini turli formulalar (masalan, Geron formulasi) va parametrlari (masalan, ikki tomoni va ular orasidagi burchak bo'yicha) orqali hisoblash keltirilgan.

Misol. Delphi dasturida uchburchak yuzini Geron formulasi, tomoni va unga tushirilgan balandligi bo'yicha, ikki tomoni va ular orasidagi burchak orqali, bitta tomoni va uchta burchagi bo'yicha topish formulalari orqali hisoblash dasturi quyidagicha ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

Bu masalani yechishimiz uchun Delphi dasturini ishga tushirib uning oynasida quyidagi tugmalarni hosil qilamiz:

1. Standart komponentalar palitrasidan “Label1”, “Label2”, “Label3” “Label4”, “Label5”, “Label6”, “Label7”, “Label8”, “Label9”, “Label10”, “Label11”, “Label12”, “Label13”, “Label14” tugmachalarini hosil qilamiz.
2. Standart komponentalar palitrasidan 5ta “Button1”, “Button2”, “Button3”, “Button4”, “Button5” tugmachalarini hosil qilamiz.
3. Standart komponentalar palitrasidan “Edit1”, “Edit2” “Edit3”, “Edit4” “Edit5”, “Edit6”, “Edit7”, “Edit8” “Edit9”, “Edit10” “Edit11”, “Edit12” tugmachalarini hosil qilamiz.

“Button2” tugmachasining dasturlash maydonchasiga dasturni kiritamiz, buning uchun “Tomoni va unga tushirigan balandligi bo‘yicha” tugmasini ikki marta tez-tez bosib, kodlarni yozish oynasiga o‘tamiz va quyidagi dasturlarni kiritamiz: **var a,h,S:real;**

begin

```
a:=strtofloat(edit4.Text);
```

```
h:=strtofloat(edit5.Text);S:=h*a/2;
```

```
label5.Caption:='S'+floattostr(s);
```

end;

“Button3” tugmachasining dasturlash maydonchasiga dasturni kiritamiz,

buning uchun “Ikki tomoni va ular orasidagi burchak bo‘yicha” tugmasini ikki marta tez-tez bosib, kodlarni yozish oynasiga o‘tamiz va quyidagi dasturlarni kiritamiz: **var a, b, y, S:real;**

begin

```
a:=strtofloat(edit6.Text);
```

```
b:=strtofloat(edit7.Text);
```

```
y:=strtofloat(edit8.Text);S:=1/2*a*b*sin(y);
```

```
label5.Caption:='S'+floattostr(s);
```

end;

“Button4” tugmachasining dasturlash maydonchasiga dasturni kiritamiz, buning uchun “Bitta tomoni va uchta burchagi bo‘yicha” tugmasini ikki marta

tez- tez bosib, kodlarni yozish oynasiga o'tamiz va quyidagi dasturlarni kiritamiz:

```
var  
a,x,y,z,S:real;  
begin  
a:=strtofloat(edit9.Text);  
x:=strtofloat(edit10.Text);  
y:=strtofloat(edit11.Text);  
z:=strtofloat(edit12.Text);  
S:=sqr(a)*sin(y)*sin(z)/2*sin(x);  
label5.Caption:='S'+floattostr(s);  
end;
```

“**Button5**” tugmachasining dasturlash maydonchasiga dasturni kiritamiz, buning uchun “Uchta tomoni bo'yicha” tugmasini ikki marta tez-tez bosib, kodlarni yozish oynasiga o'tamiz va quyidagi dasturlarni kiritamiz:

```
var  
a,b,c,p,S:real;  
begin  
a:=strtofloat(edit1.Te  
xt);  
b:=strtofloat(edit2.Te  
xt);  
c:=strtofloat(edit3.Te  
xt);if a+b<=c then  
label5.Caption:='bunday          uchburchak          mavjud  
emas'+floattostr(S)else begin  
if a+c<=b then  
label5.Caption:='bunday          uchburchak          mavjud  
emas'+floattostr(S)else begin  
if b+c<=a then  
label5.Caption:='bunday          uchburchak          mavjud  
emas'+floattostr(S)else begin  
p:=(a+b+c)/2;  
S:=sqrt(p*(p-a)*(p-b)*(p-c));  
label5.Caption:='S'+floattostr(s);  
end;
```

en

d;

en

d;

“Dasturdan chiqish” tugmasini faollashtirish uchun quyidagi dastur kiritamiz.

begin

Form1.Clos

e;end; end.

Uchburchak yuzini hisoblash uchun “F9” tugmasini tanlaymiz natijada dastur oynasi quyidagi ko‘rinishga keladi, dasturga tegishli qiymatlarni kiritamiz:

Bu oynaning belgilangan ma’lumot kiritish joylariga kerakli ma’lumotlarni kiritib har xil formulalar bo’yicha uchburchak yuzini hisoblash mumkin.

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SPECIAL ISSUE: ZAMONAVIY UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH
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